

Price Spikes and Volatility

The New Face of Global Agriculture

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Outline

- Current Situation
 - Are we headed for another food crisis?
- Why price spikes are more frequent and prices are more volatile now?
- What can be done to lower volatility?
- Some closing remarks

Impeccable Track Record

Bloomberg

Rice Export Prices to Remain Around \$600 a Ton, Economist Says

January 10, 2010, 10:06 PM EST

Rice Export Prices Unlikely to Decline, Mohanty Says (Update2)

By Luzi Ann Javier - January 11, 2010 03:12 EST

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THE ECONOMIC TIMES

英文中國郵報

The China Post

Making Headlines around the World

Chillies heat up Indonesian inflation fight
Source: Financial Times

China Moves To Control Food Price Inflation

Food price inflation: 8-10%

FAO Food Price Index

2002-2004=100

Monthly Crop Prices

\$/Mt

Data Source: Indexmundi.com

Thai 5% Broken Rice Price

(March 1998 to Dec. 2010)

US\$/t (fob)

Source of raw data: The Pink sheet, World Bank

Trend in Rice Retail Prices

Retail prices of rice and wheat in Dhaka, Bangladesh

Retail prices of rice in Indonesia

Source: Badan Pusat Statistik (BPS)

Retail prices of rice in Dong Thap, Viet Nam

Retail prices of rice and wheat in India

Source: Ministry of Consumer affairs

Cotton A-Index Price

Cents/lb

Data Source: Indexmundi.com

World & U.S. Corn Production

Data Source: USDA

World Wheat + Barley Production

Data Source: USDA

Global Rice Production

000 MT

Data Source: USDA

Extreme Weather on 2010/11 Grain Production Estimates

Million tons

Source: Various issues of World Agricultural Supply and Demand Estimates

Global Grain Stocks-To-Use Ratio

Percent

◆ Corn ■ Rice ▲ Wheat ■ Barley

Data Source: USDA

World Food Grain Consumption

000 MT

Rice Wheat

Data Source: USDA

U.S. Corn for Ethanol

Million Bushels

Source: FAPRI & USDA

World Crude Oil Price*

\$ per Barrel

Data Source: U.S. Energy Information Administration

Data Source: Indexmundi.com
*Weighted by export volume

Sharp Rise in Global Oil Consumption

Million Barrels per day

Source: U.S. Energy Information Administration

US Dollar Index

Source: Stockcharts.com

COMMODITY INDEX INVESTMENT COMPARED TO S&P GSCI SPOT PRICE COMMODITY INDEX

Source: Goldman Sachs, Bloomberg, CFTC Commitments of Traders CIT Supplement,

Source: Mike Master's Congressional Testimony

SPGSCI investment at 3-year Peak

Billion Dollars

Data Source: <http://www.reuters.com/article/idUSN0721920420110107>

What Determines Price?

Rising Price Volatility

Figure 1:

Implied price volatility of selected staple foods (in %)

Source: FAO (2010)

Note: Implied volatility represents the market's expectation of how much the price of a commodity might move in the future.

US\$/t (fob) Thai 5% Broken Rice

Source of raw data: The Pink sheet, World Bank

Food Policy Shifts

- Achieve “food security” through “food self-sufficiency”
 - Enough food for all citizens by expanding domestic production.
 - Rise in domestic support prices.
 - Input subsidies (fertilizer, seed, diesel, etc.)
 - Trade restrictions.
- Renewed focus on regional rice reserve.
- G to G trade on the rise again.

Too Much Distortions in Rice Trade

Country	Trade Restrictions
Bangladesh	Export ban; Import controls
China	Export quota; Import TRQ
India	Export ban on nonbasmati and minimum export price for basmati; Import controls
Indonesia	Export control; Import ban
Japan	Restricts imports to MMA quantity
South Korea	Restricts imports to MMA quantity
Taiwan	Restricts imports to MMA quantity
Malaysia	Imports by state agency alone.
Myanmar	Export tax
Philippines	quantitative restriction on imports

World Rice Trade

000 Metric Tons

Data source; PSD, USDA

Price Volatility on agricultural Productivity

Rice

\$ per Ton

Fertilizers

\$ per Ton

Greater variability in input and output prices negatively affect crop yields.

Food Price on Hunger

Total Number of Hungry People, 2001-2010

Millions

Source: United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO)

Price Hike on Poverty: The Case of Bangladesh

- **Jan. 2005 and March 2008: About 12 million people have been added to the poor population (Rahman et al. 2008).**
- **Head count poverty increased from 41.52% in 2006-07 to 45.86 per cent in FY 2007-08 (Raihan et al 2008), i.e., nearly 7 million people were added back into poverty.**
- **Food price hike in early 2008 had negatively impacted food consumption and nutrition situation in Bangladesh (Sulaiman, Parveen and Das 2009).**

What Needs to be Done?

- Trade and Market Reforms
 - Allow grain to move across borders
 - Let private sector do the trading.
 - Organized retailing
 - Will bring greater efficiency in the supply chain
 - Lower spread between farm gate and retail prices
 - Link producer and consumer prices more closely.
- Replace price support (MSP/mortgage price) with direct income support
 - Lower market distortions
 - Minimize budgetary costs

Transformation of the Global Soybean Market

Data Source: USDA

Chinese Dependence on Foreign Soybeans

Data Source: USDA

Rice Futures & Spot Exchange

- At the ASEAN level
 - Based in Singapore.
 - Traders from 10 member countries can buy/sell futures contracts
 - Biggest stumbling block: Government intervention in trade
- What it will achieve?
 - Transparency in price determination
 - Market stabilization
 - Improved credibility of rice trade
- Hopefully, countries will abandon the idea of forced self sufficiency.

Thai Hom Mali Grade A vs Thai 5% broken

Thai 5% vs other major grades

Closing Remarks

- In my book, we are already in crisis.
- Given lower buffer stocks+ nexus between food and fuel, expect greater price volatility and frequent spikes in the future.
 - Thin global market+ excessive trade distortions make rice price even more susceptible to supply and demand shocks
- There is no single silver bullet to fix it
 - Of course, we need to produce more.
 - Time for another revolution: Market and trade
 - More so for rice than any other commodities
 - Kick start WTO negotiation ASAP